

An Investigation of Delamination Characteristics
in Tapered Laminates

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ABSTRACT

A tapered beam subjected to tension was investigated the interlaminar stress distribution and strain energy release rate due to effect of ply dropoff and free edge. It is found that delamination growing along the tapered line will be self-arrested if the applied load remains unchanged.

INTRODUCTION

Many advanced composite helicopter rotor hubs are being designed with flapping flexures which replace bearing used in traditional designs. Typically, the flapping flexure is designed by tailoring thickness in the narrow width of the structural laminate. The change of laminate thickness, achieved by internally dropping plies, creates an eccentric load path resulting in interlaminar stresses between the plies. In addition, the narrow width of flexure laminate gives rise to high interlaminar stresses near the edges. Delamination then occurs at those interfaces where high interlaminar stresses are located. The flapping capability of composite flexures is hence limited by their delamination strength. Therefore, the application of composites in the helicopter rotor hubs spurred a need in the understanding of delamination behavior in tapered laminates used in design.

In the past few years, research efforts were focused to investigate the stress distribution in the vicinity of ply dropoff and to predict the initiation of ply failure. Kemp and Johnson[1] and Curry, Johnson and Starnes[2] used a generalized plane strain finite element to model the edge view of a tapered laminate. Interlaminar stress distribution and ply failure criterion were investigated. Free edge effect of the laminate was not included. Fish and Lee[3] studied interlaminar stress distribution due to both ply dropoff and edge effect in a tapered laminate. Salpekar, Raju and O'Brien[4] studied both interlaminar stresses and strain energy release rates of a tapered laminate due to ply dropoff only.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the delamination characteristics due to both ply dropoff and free edge in a tapered laminate. Finite element method was used. Interlaminar stresses and strain energy release rates along the line of the taper as well as along the free edge were investigated.

ANALYSIS

Two finite element models were used to investigate the taper and free edge effects of the delamination characteristics, respectively.

1. Geometry and Laminate Layup

Figure 1 shows a typical tapered laminate configuration used in this study. The laminate consists of a S2/SP250 glass/epoxy with a $(0_2, +45_3)_S$ in the thick section and a $(0_2, +45_2)_S$ in the thin section. This type of layup is a generic layup used in the helicopter rotor flexure in which the 0° plies primarily carry the centrifugal force of the rotor structure. The 45° plies adjacent to 0° ply were generally internally dropped to achieve the thickness requirement for flapping capability. As shown in Figure 1, the 0° ply was tapered to a twenty ply distance away from the termination site. Resin was assumed to fill in the void created by ply termination.

2. Finite Element Model

A) Edge View Model(Tapered Model)

A two dimensional finite element model in the X-Z plane is used to calculate the stress state in the ply dropoff region of the tapered laminate. Due to symmetry of the problem analyzed, only one quarter of the beam needs to be modeled. The general purpose finite element MSC/NASTRAN was used in this analysis. This model contains 487 CQUAD8(8-node isoparametric element) and 14 CTRIA6(6-node triangular element) membrane elements with a total of 1592 nodal points with 2 degrees of freedom per node. Fine meshes were applied to the tapered root region in both thickness and longitudinal directions. The material constants used in this study are listed in Table 1. The material constants in the Z-direction were assumed to be equal to the principal material constants in the transverse to fiber direction. Conditions to enforce symmetry at the end of the thick section and at the midplane were imposed. RBE2 (rigid) element was used at the end of the thin section to enforce uniform deformation along this section.

B) Cross-Section Model(Free-Edge Model)

Five laminate cross section models located as shown in Figure 2 were used to study the effects of free edge on the interlaminar stresses and strain energy release rates. However, only results in the cross section at taper root (Face 2) are presented in this paper. It should be noted that the 0° ply in the transition region is inclined at a constant angle relative to the mid-plane of the beam. Therefore, the material constants for the elements that model the 0° ply need to be transformed according to the inclination angle. Additionally, the neat resin region has different thickness for each model.

A generalized plane strain element for quasi-3D finite element analysis developed by Chan and Ochoa[5] was used in this study. The element has a displacement field as

$$u = \epsilon_0 x + Kxz + U(y, z)$$

$$v = Cxz + V(y, z)$$

$$w = -1/2Kx^2 - Cxy + W(y, z)$$

where ϵ_0 , uniform extension, K, longitudinal curvature and C, twisting curvature are the loading terms in the model and U, V and W constitute the stiffness matrix for the finite element. About 180 eight-node isoparametric elements were used in the model.

Table 1 Material Constants

Materials	E_1	E_2, E_3	G_{12}, G_{13}, G_{23}	$\nu_{12}, \nu_{23}, \nu_{13}$	t_{ply}
	Msi	Msi	Msi		in
S2/SP250					
Glass/Epoxy	7.2	2.1	0.8	0.288	0.0085
SP250					
Neat Resin	0.57	0.57	0.208	0.37	

3. Strain Energy Release Rate Computation

An efficient method based on the crack closure integral[6] was used to compute the strain energy release rates associated with the delamination growth. The computational scheme is shown in Figure 3. In the finite element model, double nodes are assigned along the prescribed delamination path. They are designated as I_s and J_s for nodes on upper and lower crack surfaces, respectively (see Figure 3a). Each pair of nodes have the same coordinates. We label the model C_p as the one with node pairs (I_1, J_1) to (I_p, J_p) rigidity connected. Thus, if the crack is to grow m-element length along the preselected path, we first analyze model C_{p+1} to compute the nodal force between nodes I_{p+1} and J_{p+1} . Next, the model C_p is analyzed to compute the displacement between nodes I_{p+1} and J_{p+1} .

The strain energy release rate associated with the fracture modes, mode I, mode II and mode III, is then calculated as the work required for closing the delamination. For the case of the tapered model, the G_{III} , strain energy release rate for Mode III was identically zero because plane strain conditions were assumed in the analysis.

In actual implementation, model C_p (i.e. with all (I_p, J_p) disconnected) is coded for MSC/NASTRAN. Each model C_p is then treated as a subcase by using the multi-point-constraint capability (MPC) of MSC/NASTRAN to model the actual crack configuration. In this way, the strain energy release rates for crack growth along a pre-assigned path can be computed with a single finite element analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Interlaminar stresses due to taper were obtained at each element node in the edge view model. Interlaminar stresses due to free edge, however, were calculated at Gaussian points of each element in the cross section models. All the stresses plotted were normalized by the applied strain and all the strain energy release rates normalized by square of the strain. Figure 4 shows

the interlaminar normal stress distribution normal to the taper line. High tensile stress spike occurs at the taper root and high compressive stress spike occurs at the taper hilltop. Interlaminar shear stress along the taper line is plotted in Figure 5. High interlaminar shear is observed at the taper hilltop. The interlaminar normal stress distribution across the laminate thickness at the taper root is shown in Figure 6. It is shown that the normal stress peak at this cross section is located at the 0/45 interface. The distribution of edge normal stress shown in Figure 7 also indicates that high peak occurs at the same interface. It has been suggested [7] that delamination due to inplane load will initiate at the interface where the high interlaminar normal stress is present. Therefore, an initial delamination is assumed at this critical interface. The initial delamination is then allowed to grow along the taper line or horizontally into the taper region. A small initial delamination with half-ply length in the thin section is also assumed in both delamination growth models. Figure 8 shows the total strain energy release rate ($G_T = G_I + G_{II}$) variation with respect to the delamination growing along the taper line or growing horizontally into the taper peak region. The peak of G_T is higher for delamination growing along the taper line than for delamination growing horizontally. G_T decreases as delamination grows beyond two-ply length for both cases. Like G_T , G_I , (strain energy release rate of the Mode I component of the total) is higher for delamination along the taper line than the other case. G_I decreases as delamination grows beyond two-ply length for both cases. This suggests that delamination will grow along the taper line and eventually will be self-arrested provided that the applied load remains unchanged.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions are drawn in this study.

1. An efficient method based on crack closure technique was developed to calculate strain energy release rate.
2. High interlaminar stresses occur at the interface between 0 and 45 plies.
3. For the layup used in this study. The interlaminar stresses and strain energy releases are higher due to the ply dropoff effect than the free edge effect.
4. Delamination growing along the taper line will self-arrested if the applied load remains unchanged.

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Figure 1 Tapered Laminate Configuration

Figure 2 Modeling of Longitudinal Cross Section

Figure 3 Computation Scheme of Strain Energy Release Rate

Figure 4 Normalized interlaminar stress distribution along the taper line

Figure 5 Normalized interlaminar shear distribution along the taper line

Figure 6 Normalized interlaminar normal stress through thickness due to taper

Figure 7 Interlaminar normal stress through thickness due to free edge

Figure 8 Strain energy release rate variation